

TRAINING FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF BALANCE IN LEARNING TO MOVE

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Annotation: The article presents the various approaches to definition of the terms equilibrium, balance, stability and metastability, giving the characteristics of their types. It describes the conditions of the balance preservation and the equilibrium providing system of the person. It shows the basic principles of the development of the equilibrium function, which is important for the effective training. It considers the general requirements for the development of balance function and exercise for the formation of this ability.

Keywords: roller skis, equilibrium, balance, stability, balance training, roller ski technique.

The article describes and illustrates the complex of the special physical exercises for development of balance on the roller skis, allowing you to improve the balance of the athletes of the average qualification. It defines the negative correlation of the relative growth in time of free movement for each foot on roller skis and time of free movement before training. The increase in time of the free motion on the one roller skis before training depends on the technical and functional readiness of the athlete and reduces the absolute result of the balance training. According to the obtained experimental data the tall athletes have less stable right foot, and heavy athletes have less stable left foot, so the individual recommendations are useful for balance training by anthropometric indicators. Balance training for highly qualified athletes involves carrying out the individual exercises at the beginning of the competitive season to improve moving on steep descents, not reducing the speed and keeping balance. The importance of balance and vestibular stability to many sports is undeniable. According to a number of authors, they are a criterion for high sportsmanship. In connection with early specialization, shortening of training periods and complication of sports equipment, high demands are placed on young athletes in terms of balance and vestibular stability. This necessitates the search for new ways to better and faster teach children to control their movements. Perhaps an effective way will be the optimization of the training process, taking into account the properties of the nervous system of those involved. The concept of "balance" stands out from the general and less specific concept of "dexterity", which is widespread in everyday life and in the literature on physical education. Under the balance should be understood, firstly, the ability to

purposefully build integral motor acts, and secondly, the ability to transform the developed forms of actions or switch from one to another, according to the requirements of changing conditions. These features largely coincide, but they also have their own specifics. It is not difficult to imagine, say, a student who successfully copes with learning a new combination of movements, but is unable to demonstrate it qualitatively as soon as the execution condition suddenly changes.

Vestibular stability ensures the economical use of children's energy resources, affects the amount of their use, since muscle effort accurately dosed in time, space and degree of filling and the optimal use of the corresponding relaxation phases lead to rational use of forces. The variety of exercise options needed to develop vestibular stability is a guarantee that monotony and monotony in classes can be avoided, and the joy of participating in sports activities can be ensured. Therefore, vestibular stability at school age is an urgent task of the upbringing process. Object of study: the process of physical education. Subject of research: game activity as a means of developing vestibular stability and balance in children of primary school age. Purpose: To study the influence of play activity on the formation of vestibular stability and balance in children of middle school age at physical education lessons. Tasks: To reveal the essence, meaning, classification of coordination abilities in the control of movements and biomechanical aspects of maintaining the balance of the human body.

Essence, meaning and classification of coordination abilities in motion control
One of the most important tasks of physical education is the development of motor function and the ability to control one's movements. More T.F. Lestgaft, speaking about the tasks of physical education, noted the importance of "the ability to isolate individual movements, compare with each other, consciously control them and adapt to obstacles, overcome them with the greatest possible dexterity." The coordination abilities of a person perform an important function in the control of his movements, namely, the coordination, ordering of various motor movements into a single whole of the corresponding task [20]. The importance of developing coordination abilities is explained by four main reasons: . Well-developed coordination abilities are essential prerequisites for successful physical exercise training. They influence the pace, type and method of mastering sports equipment, as well as its further stabilization and situationally appropriate diverse application. Coordination abilities lead to greater density and variability of motion control processes, to an increase in motor experience. . Only formed coordination abilities are a necessary condition for preparing children for life, work, and military service. They contribute to the efficient performance of work operations with ever-increasing demands in the process of work, increase the ability of a person to control their movements. . Coordination abilities ensure the economical use of children's energy resources, affect the amount of their use, since muscle effort accurately dosed in time, space and degree of filling and the optimal use

of the corresponding relaxation phases lead to rational use of forces. . A variety of exercise options necessary for the development of coordination abilities are a guarantee that monotony and monotony in classes can be avoided, and the joy of participating in sports activities can be ensured.

Classification of coordination abilities. Coordinating abilities are the functional capabilities of certain organs and structures of the body, the interaction of which determines the coordination of individual elements of movement into a single semantic motor action. Coordination abilities include: spatial orientation, accuracy of movement reproduction in terms of spatial, force and time parameters, static and dynamic balance. Motor-coordination abilities are understood as the ability to quickly, accurately, expediently, economically and resourcefully, that is, most perfectly, solve motor problems (especially complex and unexpected ones). Coordination movements are also called: dexterity, dexterity, statokinetic stability. Statokinetic stability - resistance to maintaining the balance of posture and movements, depends on the coordination of muscle movements and the stability of the vestibular apparatus. Afferent signals to the vestibular center come from the receptors of the eyes, stomach, muscles and receptive fields of the vestibular apparatus, which allow you to determine the position of the body in space and coordinate the movements of various muscle groups. Static stability is necessary in aiming exercises: shooting from a rifle, a gun, a pistol, a bow, throwing a ball at a target, maintaining a posture in gymnastics, and so on. Dynamic stability manifests itself in movement, especially in a changing situation, for example, in a game (football, basketball, hockey, etc.). Dynamic stability refers to the ability to resist motion sickness. For the effective formation of coordination abilities, it is necessary to develop specific ways and means of improving the corresponding types of coordination abilities based on a general approach to physical education, taking into account their place and role in the general system of human motor activity. Hence the need for classification of coordination abilities follows.

During the conversation, the parties expressed satisfaction with the development of cooperation between Tajikistan and China. Kishi yuksak embodies the virtue and dignity of egallamadan, a person of self-love, cheerfulness, morality, manners, a humanitarian, a talented person, a perfect person, a worthy noble mortal.

Vestibular stability and balance is characterized by the ability of people to control their movements. The complexity of controlling the musculoskeletal system lies in the fact that the human body consists of a significant number of biolinks that have more than a hundred degrees of freedom. The coordination of movements is nothing but overcoming the excessive degrees of freedom of our organs of movement, that is, turning them into controlled systems.

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